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Navigating the Moral Values of Senior High School Students

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Abstract

This qualitative study examined how senior high school students' moral beliefs and personal positions on moral behavior—especially when dealing with difficulties and moral conundrums—affect their academic path. This study utilized purposive sampling and was conducted using face-to-face interviews with 10 senior high school students. After careful data analysis using Moustakas' method, the study yielded five central themes: social courtesy, tangled benevolence, technology and support system behavior, upholding diversity and positive attitudes, live up with norms and standards. Moreover, the research emphasized four coping themes related to social behavior: conformity and obedience, holistic youth development, good citizenship, and support peace advocacy. Lastly, the study unveiled three overarching themes highlighting the significance of moral values within the societal fabric: demonstrating peace and a loving attitude, valuing dignity, freedom, and justice for all, and strengthening support system. In light of these insights, the study suggests that stakeholders play a crucial role in creating a holistic framework that promotes cohesion and supports the moral principles of senior high school students.

Keywords: *moral values, senior high school students, phenomenology*

Introduction

Moral values are the first aspect in life that should be developed for people to judge the situation at hand, whether it is good or bad, and to have a harmonious life. Nowadays, we can see that senior high school students face a variety of challenging moral dilemmas. Moral issues are connected to actions that have harmful impacts on individuals. According to the report of the World Health Organization in 2023, interpersonal violence is one of the top causes of death in teenagers and young people worldwide. It accounts for over a third of the mortality of male adolescents in the WHO Region of the Americas' low- and middle-income nations. In the global school-based student health survey, bullying was reported by 42% of adolescent boys and 37% of adolescent girls.

In the global context, cultural diversity across countries influences moral values, with conformity, tradition, and universal values like open-mindedness, equality, world peace, and social justice (Helkama & Sortheix, 2015). However, teenage depression contributes to 16% of global diseases and 10-20% of young people worldwide who suffer from mental illnesses, with 50% starting before age 15 and 75% before age 25 (WHO, 2023; WHO, 2020), highlighting the urgent need for mental health services.

In the Philippines, religious awareness, and morality are connected. We need religion to teach moral values like justice, peace, honesty, righteousness, brotherhood, equality, virtue, tolerance, sacrifice, and helping others in need. However, Hauser and Schwarz (2016) assert that there is no discernible difference between atheists and those with religious backgrounds in their moral judgments when it comes to moral quandaries that are unknown to them. In Davao Region, Acero (2016) stated that a set of morally defensible ideas, norms, rules, and behaviors are referred to as conduct. However, Madelo (2015) argued that no connection exists between students' acquisition of 21st-century abilities and the principles of unconditional love and collaboration.

Addressing the pressing moral dilemmas faced by today's youth is crucial, given the alarming outcomes and abuses reported. Statistics from the Committee on Health reveal a significant rise in suicide cases in Davao City (Cortez, 2023), which also ranks fifth in the nation for teenage pregnancies (Palicte, 2022). While substantial research exists on the foundations of morality and teachers' perspectives on moral education, less attention has been given to the moral values upheld by senior high school students and the factors influencing these values. This study is urgently needed to impact the participants positively and aid in developing their moral values. It will also provide a foundation for future research, addressing the current gap in local studies on the moral values of senior high school students.

Research Questions

This study aimed to explore the values and dilemmas of senior high school students and how the phenomenon affects their lives and academic journey. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. How do senior high school students uphold moral values?
2. How do senior high school students cope with social behavior?
3. What insights can the participants contribute to the importance of moral values in the social fabric?

Literature Review

Moral Foundations of High School Students

The foundations of man's personality are morality. Terms like "nature," "personality," "character," and "temperament," which is

components of everyone's personality and character, are used to characterize morality. In addition, the process of developing one's mental, emotional, and behavioral abilities that contribute to the formation of one's moral behavior is known as moral maturity. The word "morality," which is included, has three interpretations: character (temperament, personality, virtue), custom (custom, tradition, circumcision), and religion. Other definitions of morality include friendships, empathy, respect and responsibility, decision-making, and divine rules (Gunner, 2020). Furthermore, Tan et al. (2018) emphasized that values are the guiding principles and essential beliefs that serve as broad guidelines for behavior and the standards for which specific acts are measured that are considered admirable or good. Love, equality, freedom, justice, happiness, security, peace of mind, and truth are a few examples of values. Therefore, students should learn social values to become good citizens. A good citizen upholds moral values and is accountable to their family, community, and country to preserve a steady or peaceful relationship with others; he or she considers others before acting. Additionally, a good person is obedient to the law and dedicated to community improvement. Furthermore, morality has two functions: promoting ideals and justice and maintaining social stability; hence, it is related to moral values navigation (Helkama & Sortheix, 2015). Considering these definitions, senior high school students comprise a significant portion of society. Hence, it is crucial to understand their perspectives on moral values.

Role of Parents in Inculcating Values

Studies show that students with parents who have higher educational levels tend to have better moral judgment (Aybek et al., 2015). Parents, as primary role models, play a crucial role in shaping their children's behavior and morals. Effective parenting requires leading by example, making sacrifices, and committing time and effort. Good manners, honesty, and respect for authority should be taught early on, as these are essential for polite behavior. Parents must be mindful of their own actions and avoid misleading their children, while also helping them manage temper tantrums (Mary, 2016).

Dark Triad Traits Affect and Influence One's Moral Values

Negative behavior can harm moral qualities like trust and empathy. Spitefulness, driven by a desire to inflict harm on others despite personal cost, often aligns with dark personality traits such as control, deceit, and exploitation (Zeigler-Hill et al., 2015; Noser et al., 2015). This behavior may result from a lack of understanding others' feelings and can undermine fairness in social systems. Traits like narcissism, psychopathy, and sadism, part of the "dark" personality traits, suggest that harmful behaviors stem more from personality than morality (Jonason et al., 2017). Research shows that moral violations may increase when protecting others from harm, and compassion can lead to morally complex decisions like lying to benefit others (Zhu et al., 2020; Wood et al., 2016; Lupoli et al., 2017). Balancing light and dark traits, emphasizing social trust and less aggression, can enhance personality development and life satisfaction (Neumann et al., 2020).

Social Media as Other Factor of Moral Values

Identity is an integrated system of physical, psychological, moral, and social elements that defines and unites an individual (Mitchell et al., 2016; Mohsen, 2018). With the rise of social media, especially among youth, there is a growing concern about its impact on social relations and identity. Social media can influence youth self-esteem and values, often leading them to disconnect from their communities (Elsayed, 2021). While social media offers communication benefits, it also presents challenges, such as disrupting family dynamics and influencing emotional development (Hamdi, 2018). Families should monitor their teens' online activities and guide them to positive resources. It is crucial for families, schools, and communities to address social media's effects on youth identities (Bu Abdullah, 2016).

Addressing Youth Vulnerabilities

Youth face severe challenges: 1 in 8 experience sexual violence, suicide is the second leading cause of death among 15-19-year-olds, and 16% of global disease burden in this age group is due to depression (Shahedifar et al., 2020; WHO, 2023). Mental health issues often start before age 15, with many cases going untreated (World Health Organization, 2020). Teen alcohol use exacerbates risky behaviors, with over 155 million teenage drinkers globally. Immediate access to mental health services and preventive care is crucial (Zifkin et al., 2021). Moral values like empathy, respect, and responsibility are essential for healthy development and societal well-being (Dhope, 2022). Education and a supportive environment are key to fostering these values and addressing youth vulnerabilities. Collaboration among families, schools, and communities is vital to build a nurturing environment that supports youth resilience and well-being (Turkkahraman, 2015).

Methodology

Participants

In this study, the researchers used purposive sampling, highlighted by Yin (2011) as crucial in non-probability sampling, to select key participants. This method, common in qualitative research, optimizes resource use by selecting information-rich cases (Patton, 2002). We chose senior high school students from Grades 11 and 12 at St. John Paul II College of Davao, enrolled in the second semester of 2022-2023 and aged 18 or older. Participants needed to be knowledgeable about moral values. We excluded students with speech disabilities, those under 18, and those under the influence of alcohol during interviews.

Instrument

For a qualitative study, the researchers analyzed data using Moustakas' (1994) Transcendental Approach: (1) avoiding biases, (2) analyzing key statements, (3) exploring new perspectives, and (4) unifying themes. This method revealed hidden themes and true intentions. Moreover, the researchers refined interpretations and used participant quotes to capture their moral values.

Procedure

The researchers formulated data questions and coordinated with their adviser. After validating the interview guide protocols and questions, the researchers obtained permission from the senior high school principal. Using purposive sampling, participants were selected based on specific criteria. Then, the research topic was introduced, allowing them to decide on participation. Participants who agreed chose pseudonyms to protect their privacy per R.A. 10173.

Participants signed informed consent forms, clarifying voluntary participation and confidentiality. The researchers took field notes during interviews to track the duration and visits needed for data saturation, aiming to explore participants' experiences with moral values.

At St. John Paul II College of Davao, 10 senior high school students participated. In-depth interviews provided deep insights (Carter et al., 2014; Fontana & Frey, 2000). After gathering data, the researchers used data triangulation to enhance validity and reliability (Leech & Onwuegbuzie, 2007; Altrichter et al., 1996; Turner & Turner, 2009), ensuring a comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon.

Ethical Considerations

This study adheres to Guba's (1981) principles for trustworthiness in qualitative research, ensuring rigor in planning, structure, and reporting to accurately capture participant experiences. It assesses validity using criteria like credibility, confirmability, transferability, and dependability from Lincoln and Guba's (1985) model.

To establish credibility, rigorous methods explore senior high school students' moral values and experiences, ensuring accurate data interpretation (Patton, 1999). Confirmability is maintained by seeking consistent, replicable results (Shenton, 2004). Transferability focuses on practical application in similar contexts (Anney, 2014). Dependability is ensured through rigorous validation of study outputs and interpretations (Miller, 1997).

Results and Discussion

This section presents the outcome of the qualitative analysis of the research questions' answers. The results are presented based on the emerging themes and core ideas.

Profile of the Conversational Partners

The findings of the study are presented in Matrices generated from the thematic analysis.

Matrix 1 is the information of the participants in our study. There were 10 senior high school students from this educational institution for Academic Year 2022-2023, with equal representation: 5 participants from Grade 11 and 5 participants from Grade 12. Gender representation was equally balanced, with 5 male and 5 female participants. All participants are currently residing in Davao City.

It is important to note that during data handling, strict ethical considerations were observed to ensure the confidentiality and privacy of the participants. Any potential confidentiality dilemmas were carefully addressed, and the data were reported with appropriate measures to protect the identity of the participants. Therefore, to protect them from gossip and criticisms from the manuscript's readers, we allowed them to provide pseudonyms without compromising the contextual information. The in-depth interview participants are as follows: Qurain, Sasha, Paw, Pao-Pao, Aljoe, Jai, Mavsss, Bro, Crhm, and Maux.

Matrix 1. Profile of the Participants

<i>Category</i>	<i>Assumed Name</i>	<i>Gender</i>	<i>Location</i>	<i>Level</i>	<i>Study Group</i>
NMVSHSS_P1	Qurain	Male	Davao City	11	Interview
NMVSHSS_P2	Sasha	Female	Davao City	11	Interview
NMVSHSS_P3	Paw	Female	Davao City	11	Interview
NMVSHSS_P4	Pao-Pao	Male	Davao City	11	Interview
NMVSHSS_P5	Aljoe	Male	Davao City	11	Interview
NMVSHSS_P6	Jai	Female	Davao City	12	Interview
NMVSHSS_P7	Mavsss	Male	Davao City	12	Interview
NMVSHSS_P8	Bro	Male	Davao City	12	Interview
NMVSHSS_P9	Crhm	Female	Davao City	12	Interview
NMVSHSS_P10	Maux	Female	Davao City	12	Interview

Matrix 2. Themes and Core Ideas of How Senior High School Students Uphold their Moral Values

<i>Themes</i>	<i>Core Ideas</i>
Social Courtesy	Respectful and Compassionate Generous and Honest Helpful and God-fearing Responsible and Compromise Obedient and Equality Discipline and Empathy Trusted Environment and Monotheist
Tangled Benevolence	Exploitation Hampers Values, Trust, and Help Ingratitude Fear Lowers Values and Hinders Altruism Abuse, Lies, and Trauma lead to Trust Issues Bullying alters Morals and causes Emotional Harm Profanity Adoption fosters Freedom and Camaraderie Unreciprocated Dependence breeds Caution and erodes Trust
Technology and Support System Behavior	Friends Self-esteem Family Religion Social Media Social Issues Diversity
Technology and Support System Behavior	Gestures and Custom Honor Diverse People
Live Up to the Norms and Standards	Responsibility, Compromise, and Obedience. Respect Other's Beliefs and Perspectives Faith fosters Self-awareness and embraces Humility Uphold Morals, Self-reflect, and Resist Negative Influences Social Context Familiarity and Trust in Relationships Family Values Uphold Moral Principles Practice Honesty and Renew Oneself Guidance, Foster Care, Responsibility, and Honesty Respect, Accountability, and Media Literacy Conflict Resolution, Ethical Dilemmas, and Reciprocity Kindness and Humility towards Others Behave with Personal Values and Beliefs Positive Attributes, Compromise, and Empathy Self-understanding, Consistency, and Genuine Friendships Solve Issues Ethically and Critically with Skepticism

Matrix 3. Themes and Core Ideas of How Senior High School Students Cope with the Mandate of Social Behavior

<i>Themes</i>	<i>Core Ideas</i>
Conformity and Obedience	Observe Social Norms, Hygiene, and Religious Practices Enforcement to Avoid Compulsive Behavior and Empathy Consequence for Non-compliance, Goal-oriented Behavior Achieving Common Goals Positively impacts Outcomes Social Responsibility, Effective Communication, Law-abiding Citizen and Compliance to the Rules and Regulations Independence, Time Management, and Environmental Awareness Kindness shows Genuine Care, Perceived Respect and Cooperation
Youth Holistic Approach Development	Empower Individuals, Foster Relationships, and Prevent Gossip Promote Accountability and Awareness for Individual Behavior Oppose Negativity, Care for Others, and Promote Parental Guidance Model Healthy Relationships, Foster Positivity, Communicate Effectively Support Friends with Depression and Offer Companionship Lead by Example, Advocate Education, and Spirituality Follow Religion's Teachings for Self-growth and Values Cope with Secrecy, Support, Act Against Cruelty, and Resiliency
Good Citizenship	Respect Authority and Adhere to Social Mandate Advocate Individual Rights and Dignity, and Nurture Relationships

Support Peace Advocacy	Pursue Peaceful Living, Organize, and Avoid Conflict Maintain Inner Peace and Support Law and Order Follow Norms to Avoid Conflict Exemplify Good Morals for Common Welfare Improve Family Bonds, and Enhance Cooperation with Others Undisturbed Living can Free from Distraction and Promote a Safe Environment Enhance Community Interaction and Positive Relationship Live with Happiness, Make Friends and Earn Respect Promote Harmonious Living, and Ensure Personal Well-being Choose Actions Wisely, Be Faithful, and Avoid Problems Develop Personal Growth, Discipline, and Achieve Success
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Matrix 4. Themes and Core Ideas of the Contribution of the Participants on the Importance of Moral Values in Social Fabric

Themes	Core Ideas
Demonstrating Peace and Loving Attitude	Acceptance, Honesty, Optimism, and Ethics Kindness and Independence Improve Judgment Knowledgeable and Promote Reciprocity Loyalty, Integrity, and Truthfulness Self-awareness and Value of Others' Perspectives and Emotions Problem-solving Skills that are Associated with Moral Values Humility, Mindfulness and Self-Compassion Resiliency, Steadfastness, Avoid Exploitation
Valuing Dignity, Freedom, and Justice for All	Respect Others' Beliefs an Rights, Acceptance of Others' Choices and Decisions Support Equality, Honesty, and Critical Thinking Select Right Conduct and Grasp Complexity Understand Others' Actions and Compromise Kindness, Reciprocity, and Fair Judgment Uphold the Doctrines of Religion
Strengthening Support System	Caring Family teaches Moral Values, and Shares Experiences Religion instills Respect for Fellow Beings Schools Educate, Nurture, and Become Moral Knowledge Center

The study's findings are discussed in this chapter in relation to the research questions stated in Chapter One. After a brief review of the questions and the resulting emerging themes, interpretations that attempted to provide logical explanations were examined.

Senior high school students uphold their moral values in light of emerging themes: Social courtesy, tangled benevolence, technology and support system behavior, upholding diversity and positive attitudes, and live up the norms and standards. Senior high school students are eager to engage in positive social interactions, showing respect, consideration, and good manners to create a harmonious environment and foster effective communication. However, as they navigate their interpersonal relationships, they may encounter challenges like exploitation, bullying, and negative peer behavior, which can influence their moral values and cause them to adjust their principles to avoid conflict and maintain inner peace. Technology and social media also play a role in shaping their moral standards. Despite these challenges, the senior high school students remain committed to fostering a sense of belonging, promoting inclusivity, and adhering to societal and communal norms, such as appropriate behavior, respect for personal boundaries, and cultural customs.

Senior high school students cope with their social behavior provided with following emerging themes: Conformity and obedience, youth holistic approach development, good citizenship, and support for peace advocacy. Senior high school students diligently follow social rules and authority, understanding that conformity can influence behavior, attitudes, and beliefs to align with societal norms. With strong support and unwavering moral values, they are committed to discerning right from wrong and serving as role models. Through citizenship education and respect for authority, law, and order, they contribute to creating a harmonious society. Observing violence and crime in the society motivates them to support peace and positively impact others.

The contribution of the participants on the importance of moral values in the social fabric: demonstrating peace and loving attitude, valuing dignity, freedom and justice for all, strengthening and supporting the system. As senior high school students mature, they gain a deeper understanding of the importance of peace, love, and positive relationships, while learning to treat others with dignity and respect, regardless of background.

High school presents challenges like academic pressures and social changes, but a strong support system provides the emotional support, guidance, and resources needed to navigate these difficulties and maintain well-being.

Conclusions

In recent times, the mental health of senior high school students has recently become a major concern as they deal with stress, anxiety, depression, and other challenges that deeply affect their lives. Senior high school students seek more awareness, support, and resources to improve their mental well-being. This study has identified key themes and insights related to their moral values, which provide a foundation for practical solutions to address their needs.

Senior high school students strive to uphold their morals, focusing on social courtesy, kindness, responsible technology use, supportive behavior, diversity, and positive attitudes while following societal norms. However, as they navigate diverse settings and face challenging situations, they may encounter moral dilemmas that impact their emotions, perceptions, and sense of identity, leading them to question the ethics of their actions. Technological advancements also play a role in shaping their moral values. Therefore, social institutions including family, religion, and schools must provide strong guidance and support to help these students achieve their goals and become exemplary individuals. Educational campaigns in communities and schools can reduce mental health stigma, raise awareness, and equip families to support young people at risk (Simkiss et al., 2020). Social institutions such as family, religion, schools, and government can provide support by fostering open communication, modeling positive behavior, teaching empathy, guiding technology use, and promoting community involvement. These strategies can improve mental health outcomes and create a more supportive environment for senior high school students.

Senior high school students manage their social behavior through conformity, youth development, good citizenship, and peace advocacy. They believe these practices promote social integration, growth, responsible citizenship, and conflict resolution, aligning with values of solidarity, justice, and equality (Veugelers et al., 2015). Educators should courageously address injustices and acknowledge the sociopolitical context (Gorski, 2016). Moreover, teachers passionate about equity should challenge behaviors that perpetuate inequality (Cochran-Smith et al., 2016). Therefore, classroom discussions are essential for developing critical thinking skills and understanding pedagogical principles (Kim & Wilkinson, 2019; Oyler, 2019). Hence, educators should focus on developing students' social skills, adherence to rules, civic engagement, and commitment to peace by organizing peace-building activities, facilitating conflict resolution discussions, teaching tolerance, and promoting community service and social responsibility.

Senior high school students promote moral values by embodying peace, love, dignity, freedom, and justice. Their actions enhance the school environment and foster social cohesion. When schools prioritize fairness and compassion alongside academics, students' moral identities are shaped (Szumski et al., 2020). Hence, guidance coordinators should support this by organizing empathy workshops, offering leadership roles, implementing anti-bullying programs, and engaging parents and the community through workshops, service partnerships, and guest speakers. School administrators and teachers need to be aware of students' needs to provide tailored support and create an environment that maximizes their potential. Hence, schools should help students set goals, understand challenges, and uphold moral principles. Despite advancements, there's a significant gap in mental health support for young people, requiring urgent action to improve access to these services. Therefore, effective collaboration among stakeholders is crucial to develop a unified approach that fosters diversity, responsibility, community engagement, and ethical decision-making. Addressing this gap will ensure that comprehensive mental health services are available to all students, supporting their well-being and development.

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